

BRIEF REPORT OPEN ACCESS

Exploring the Association of Time-After-Death on Psychological Distress in Parents Who Lost a Child to Cancer

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Received: 6 August 2025 | **Revised:** 2 September 2025 | **Accepted:** 8 September 2025

Funding: This study was funded by the Swiss Cancer Research (Grant No. KFS-4995-02-2020) and Cancer League Central Switzerland.

Keywords: anxiety | bereavement | childhood cancer | depression | parents | psychological distress

ABSTRACT

We conducted a cross-sectional survey of 101 bereaved parents in Switzerland to determine the association between time-after-death and psychological distress. Eligible deceased children were identified via the national registry and forwarded to former treating pediatric oncology centers, which then contacted the parents. Psychological distress was measured using the Brief Symptom Inventory (BSI-18). Time-after-death ranged from 2 to 24 years (mean = 11.3, SD = 5.6). Linear regression and spline models showed no significant association between time-after-death and psychological distress. Our findings suggest that time-after-death alone does not predict parental psychological distress.

1 | Introduction

The death of a child is recognized as one of the most traumatic events in a parent's life [1]. Although many bereaved parents eventually find ways to adapt to their loss, some continue to experience intense and prolonged psychological distress [2–4]. In childhood cancer, this emotional burden is aggravated by prolonged caregiving, enduring hope for a cure, and repeated exposure to medical trauma during the child's treatment.

Despite extensive research on the negative outcomes of parental bereavement following childhood cancer, significant gaps remain in understanding long-term psychological outcomes beyond 5–10 years post-bereavement [1–3]. Previous research on the association of time and psychological distress has primarily used linear

modeling approaches, which may overlook potential non-linear associations.

We aimed to explore if the time after a child's death has an influence on psychological distress in parents, whether it decreases, remains stable, or increases, and explore if there is a non-linear association.

2 | Methods

This is a cross-sectional study in Switzerland that aimed to examine the psychosocial outcomes among bereaved parents whose child died from cancer. Study procedures are described in our previous publication [4, 5].

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2.1 | Setting and Population

Eligible participants were parents of children who: (a) were diagnosed with cancer, (b) were aged ≤ 18 years at diagnosis, (c) received treatment in Switzerland, and (d) died from cancer ≥ 1 year before study participation.

The Swiss Childhood Cancer Registry (ChCR) provided a list of eligible cases to three participating pediatric oncology units in the country. Hospital staff confirmed the contact information using clinical records and excluded families considered unsuitable for contact due to clinical or personal reasons. The unit staff sent invitation packages to eligible parents, including an information sheet, an informed consent form, a questionnaire per parent, and prepaid return envelopes. Parents were asked to complete the questionnaires on paper or online (Qualtrics). The collaborating clinical centers placed reminder phone calls to non-responders starting 5 weeks after the initial mailing. Parent support organizations also shared study information through their networks, and interested parents contacted the study team directly. Data collection was conducted between July 2022 and 2023.

2.2 | Measure

The questionnaire covered psychological health, overall well-being, end-of-life and bereavement experiences, and support needs and preferences. It contained 192 items and required approximately 60–90 min to complete. The questionnaire also underwent face and expert validation prior to implementation.

Specifically for this study, psychological distress was assessed using the Brief Symptom Inventory-18 (BSI-18) [6–8]. The tool assesses somatization, depression, and anxiety, and a Global Severity Index (GSI), representing overall psychological distress. The BSI-18 has been validated in Switzerland [8] and showed high internal consistency (Cronbach's α somatization: 0.77, depression: 0.92, anxiety: 0.90, and GSI: 0.94). Raw sum scores were converted into standardized *T*-scores (mean = 50, standard deviation = 10) based on German normative data [6]. Clinical distress was defined as a *T*-score ≥ 63 on the GSI or on at least two symptom scales.

2.3 | Data Analysis

We explored three methods to determine the association of time after the child's death and parental psychological distress. First, we fitted a linear regression using GSI as the dependent variable and time-after-death as the independent variable, both treated as continuous variables. Second, we divided the population into three groups according to time-after-death: recent (1–5 years), intermediate (6–10 years), and long-term (> 10 years). We fitted another linear regression with GSI as a continuous dependent variable and bereavement length (recent, intermediate, long-term) as the independent categorical variable. Crude and adjusted models (accounting for sociodemographic differences) were fitted, and marginal means were predicted to demonstrate the difference in GSI among the three groups. Third, we explored the non-linear pattern of the association of time-after-death and GSI by fitting a restricted cubic spline. We used a model using con-

tinuous GSI as the dependent variable and the time-after-death (with four randomly assigned knots) as the independent variable. The `mkspline2` package was used, and plots were done using the smoothing parameters according to the `adjustrcspline` package.

All analyses were done using Stata 19.5 (StataCorp, TX). All tests were two-tailed, with *p* values < 0.05 considered statistically significant.

2.4 | Ethical Considerations

The study was approved by the Ethics Committee of Northwest and Central Switzerland (EKNZ 2021-00906, August 4, 2021). All participants provided written informed consent. Data were de-identified before analysis and stored on secure university servers with access limited to study investigators. The information sheet emphasized the sensitivity of the topic and explained that the study aimed to improve psychosocial support services to encourage participation. Contact details of investigators were provided for questions or in case there was a need for support.

3 | Results

The ChCR identified 388 deceased children, of which 262 were contacted by the three participating oncology units. A total of 96 parents of 77 deceased children participated (response rate: 29.8%). Seven additional parents of four cases contacted the study team independently. The final sample comprised 101 parents of 80 cases (21 parent couples, 59 individual parent respondents (46 mothers and 13 fathers; Table 1). Time-after-death ranged from 2 to 24 years (mean = 11.3, SD = 5.6).

Mean scores for GSI (mean = 50.4, SD = 9.3), somatization (49.7 ± 8.5), depression (47.8 ± 9.4), and anxiety (52.2 ± 9.5) were all within normative ranges compared with population norms [8]. No statistically significant differences were observed among bereaved parents with recent, intermediate, and long-term time-after-death in crude or adjusted analyses. Neither linear nor spline regression demonstrated a statistically significant association (Figure 1). Clinical distress was identified in 11 participants (10.9%), with no difference among recent, intermediate, and long-term bereaved parents (Table 1).

4 | Discussion

Our findings show that psychological distress remains stable over time [9, 10] and within norms of the general population. The stable pattern of psychological distress can be interpreted in several ways. First, grief reaction, coping strategies, and resilience are critical factors to consider when examining long-term psychological consequences after loss. Changes in these adaptive mechanisms over time, seen in longitudinal studies [11], may have moderated the association between psychological distress and time-after-death. An alternative interpretation suggests that bereaved parents, similar to the general population, may experience psychological distress at any time for reasons not related to their child's death [12, 13]. Psychological symptoms

TABLE 1 | Sociodemographic, child, cancer-related characteristics, and psychological distress of bereaved parents divided according to length of bereavement.

	Total	Recent	Intermediate	Long-term	p value
<i>N</i>	101 (100.0%)	20 (19.8%)	26 (25.7%)	55 (54.5%)	
Time-after-death (years)	11.3 (5.6)	4.1 (1.1)	7.7 (1.5)	15.5 (3.5)	
	2–24 years	1–5 years	6 to 10 years	> 10 years	
Sociodemographic characteristics					
Age (years)	53.8 (8.1)	47.5 (5.9)	53.3 (7.8)	56.5 (7.7)	< 0.001 ^a
Age category					
< 50 years	29 (29.3%)	10 (50.0%)	8 (30.8%)	11 (20.8%)	0.014 ^a
50–60 years	44 (44.4%)	10 (50.0%)	12 (46.2%)	22 (41.5%)	
> 60 years	26 (26.3%)	0 (0.0%)	6 (23.1%)	20 (37.7%)	
Sex					
Male	35 (34.7%)	8 (40.0%)	8 (30.8%)	19 (34.5%)	0.808
Female	66 (65.3%)	12 (60.0%)	18 (69.2%)	36 (65.5%)	
Education					
Compulsory schooling	5 (5.0%)	1 (5.0%)	1 (3.8%)	3 (5.6%)	0.612
Vocational training	64 (64.0%)	11 (55.0%)	15 (57.7%)	38 (70.4%)	
University	31 (31.0%)	8 (40.0%)	10 (38.5%)	13 (24.1%)	
Employment					
Unemployed	25 (25.0%)	4 (20.0%)	8 (30.8%)	13 (24.1%)	0.686
Employed	75 (75.0%)	16 (80.0%)	18 (69.2%)	41 (75.9%)	
Household income					
< 6000 CHF / month	13 (14.8%)	3 (15.8%)	3 (12.5%)	7 (15.6%)	0.934
> / = 6000 CHF / month	75 (85.2%)	16 (84.2%)	21 (87.5%)	38 (84.4%)	
Migration background					
No migration background	60 (81.1%)	13 (86.7%)	13 (68.4%)	34 (85.0%)	0.260
Migration background	14 (18.9%)	2 (13.3%)	6 (31.6%)	6 (15.0%)	
Practicing religion					
No	66 (69.5%)	12 (60.0%)	17 (68.0%)	37 (74.0%)	0.508
Yes	29 (30.5%)	8 (40.0%)	8 (32.0%)	13 (26.0%)	
Civil status					
Single/divorced	17 (17.2%)	3 (15.0%)	3 (12.0%)	11 (20.4%)	0.630
Married	82 (82.8%)	17 (85.0%)	22 (88.0%)	43 (79.6%)	
Child- or cancer-related characteristics					
Location of death					
Healthcare facility	34 (43.0%)	8 (47.1%)	6 (30.0%)	20 (47.6%)	0.395
Home	45 (57.0%)	9 (52.9%)	14 (70.0%)	45 (57.0%)	
Diagnosis					
Leukemia/lymphoma	21 (26.6%)	5 (29.4%)	5 (25.0%)	11 (26.2%)	0.341
CNS tumor	36 (45.6%)	9 (52.9%)	6 (30.0%)	21 (50.0%)	
Others	22 (27.8%)	3 (17.6%)	9 (45.0%)	10 (23.8%)	
Sex of the child					
Male	44 (55.7%)	11 (64.7%)	15 (75.0%)	18 (42.9%)	0.041 ^a
Female	35 (44.3%)	6 (35.3%)	5 (25.0%)	35 (57.1%)	

(Continues)

TABLE 1 | (Continued)

	Total	Recent	Intermediate	Long-term	p value
Child's age at diagnosis					
Infant < 1 year	6 (7.6%)	2 (11.8%)	1 (5.0%)	3 (7.1%)	0.948
Early child 1–5 years	24 (30.4%)	5 (29.4%)	5 (25.0%)	14 (33.3%)	
Late child 6–10 years	22 (27.8%)	5 (29.4%)	7 (35.0%)	10 (23.8%)	
Adolescent > 10 years	27 (34.2%)	5 (29.4%)	7 (35.0%)	15 (35.7%)	
Child's age at death					
Infant < 1 year	3 (3.8%)	1 (5.9%)	0 (0.0%)	2 (4.8%)	0.729
Early child 1–5 years	14 (17.7%)	2 (11.8%)	3 (15.0%)	9 (21.4%)	
Late child 6–10 years	23 (29.1%)	7 (41.2%)	5 (25.0%)	11 (26.2%)	
Adolescent > 10 years	39 (49.4%)	7 (41.2%)	12 (60.0%)	20 (47.6%)	
Psychological distress (BSI-18)					
Global Severity Index	50.4 (9.3)	52.2 (11.5)	49.9 (6.8)	50.0 (9.7)	0.636
GSI (adjusted) ^a		50.8 (10.1)	49.4 (9.8)	50.9 (10.0)	
Somatization	49.7 (8.5)	50.5 (9.3)	48.7 (7.4)	49.9 (8.7)	0.753
Somatization (adjusted) ^b		49.9 (9.3)	48.8 (9.1)	50.2 (9.2)	
Anxiety	47.8 (9.4)	48.4 (11.3)	47.8 (7.5)	47.6 (9.6)	0.957
Anxiety (adjusted) ^b		46.5 (10.1)	47.7 (9.9)	48.5 (10.1)	
Depression	52.2 (9.5)	55.6 (11.5)	51.2 (6.7)	51.4 (9.8)	0.205
Depression (adjusted) ^b		54.9 (10.2)	50.5 (9.9)	52.1 (10.1)	
Caseness					
No	90 (89.1%)	16 (80.0%)	25 (96.2%)	49 (89.1%)	0.219
Yes	11 (10.9%)	4 (20.0%)	1 (3.8%)	6 (10.9%)	

Abbreviations: CHF, Swiss Francs; CNS, central nervous system; GSI, Global Severity Index.

^ap value < 0.05, statistically significantly different among bereaved parents with recent, intermediate, and long-term time-after-death.

^bMarginal means from the regression model adjusting for age and sex of the child, which were shown to be different among bereaved parents with recent, intermediate, and long-term time-after-death.

may thus reflect concurrent life stressors rather than exclusively grief-related pathology. Unfortunately, our findings remain exploratory, and further analyses are still needed to test each hypothesis.

Most studies have investigated negative outcomes (prolonged grief and psychological distress) and time-after-death, using linear models. However, human responses often show non-linear patterns [14]. Our study applied a more comprehensive approach by modeling the association of psychological distress and time-after-death both linearly and non-linearly using categorical predictors and splines. Also, most studies on childhood cancer bereaved parents focused on 5–10 years after child loss [9, 10, 15]. Our study included parents up to 24 years after their loss.

A limitation is the relatively low participation rate, which is common in studies involving bereaved parents due to the emotional burden of revisiting painful experiences [16, 17]. To mitigate the impact of a limited sample size, a comprehensive case identification was conducted using the nationwide registry (ChCR), and reminder calls were made to improve recruitment. Second, gate-keeping bias may have occurred during hospital screening, where

individuals with unstable psychological status may have been excluded, potentially leading to an overrepresentation of participants with better psychological outcomes. Third, self-selection bias is possible, as individuals with more favorable mental health are more likely to participate than those with adverse outcomes [16]. However, some bereaved parents may participate to help others by sharing their experiences, which partly offsets this bias [16]. Our sample closely resembled non-participants in the ChCR data, further supporting the representativeness of the study population. Finally, our findings are based on cross-sectional analysis, such that contextual changes may affect psychological distress more than child loss. For example, because parents are more likely to engage in support groups during the early bereavement phase and less likely in later phases, our results may underestimate distress in the initial period and overestimate it in later stages.

Support for bereaved parents often declines, yet some experience long-term psychological distress [18]. Our findings underline the need for long-term follow-up rather than limiting care to the immediate bereavement phase. Routine screening for psychological outcomes should be embedded in pediatric oncology

FIGURE 1 | Psychological distress (GSI, y-axis) as a function of time-after-death (x-axis). The linear and spline models strongly suggest that psychological distress is not associated with time-after-death (LR = 1.16, p value = 0.559, linear vs. spline model). Red line shows the fitted linear model. Blue line shows the fitted spline model with 95% confidence interval, with overlapping intervals indicated by shading. Box marks the observed range of BSI scores.

follow-up, with clear referral pathways to specialized care [18, 19]. Implementing transitional bereavement care models can link hospital services, primary care, and community resources, ensuring continuity and tailored support [20]. This approach can help reduce enduring long-term psychosocial hardship among bereaved families.

5 | Conclusion

Our finding suggests that time-after-death is not associated with psychological distress in parents whose child died from cancer. Contextual factors such as grief reactions, resilience, and socioeconomic conditions should be further examined to understand their role in long-term psychological distress.

Author Contributions

P.F.R. and G.M. conceptualized the study. P.F.R. and J.D. performed the analysis. P.F.R., J.D., A.K.V., E.D.C., E.C.P., and G.M. wrote the first draft of the manuscript. K.S., A.O.V.B., E.M.T., and E.B. recruited participants, reviewed the draft, and provided expert feedback. E.M.T., E.B., and G.M. secured funding. G.M. supervised the data collection and analysis. All authors approved the manuscript.

Acknowledgments

We thank the participating hospitals and the parents who participated in our survey. We also acknowledge and appreciate the help of our interns, Katja Rueesch, Simone Walde-Foehn, Kathleen Ostheim, Laura Haxhosaj, and Sebastian Thackwell, and Dr. Manya Hendriks.

Open access publishing facilitated by Universitat Luzern, as part of the Wiley - Universitat Luzern agreement via the Consortium Of Swiss Academic Libraries.

Ethics Statement

Ethical approval was granted through the Ethics Committee of North-west and Central Switzerland (EKNZ 2021-00906; 04 August 2021). The research was conducted in accordance with the principles of the Declaration of Helsinki. The study is compliant with the Swiss Human Research Act (810.30 Federal Act of September 30, 2011 on Research involving Human Beings) and Federal Regulations on Data Protection (235.1 Federal Act on Data Protection of September 25, 2020). Written informed consent was obtained from all study participants.

Conflicts of Interest

The authors declare no conflicts of interest.

Data Availability Statement

Data can be made available upon reasonable request from the corresponding author.

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